

1 **NLRP7 and NLRP12 are basic components of a NLR-based system that secures the breast whose**
2 **origin is associated with the primitive nature of the mammary organ.**

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7 We present here the concept supported by measurement of total transcription in humans that the human
8 breast is an organ with restricted access and of distinct ecologic status whose pluripotency marked by
9 *NLRP7* and *NLRP12* is an intrinsic component of the gene expression signature of the healthy human
10 breast whose origin can be ascribed to function of these NLR sensors in stem cells associated with the
11 pluripotent state those but which has become intertwined with primitive nature of the mammary organ.

12 Citations

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